

Rod & Pin Optimization on 6.4L Heavy Duty Engine for bushing wear and noise reduction

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Abstract

This research paper on a problem that has persisted over the years in heavy-duty engines is commonly known as "pin tick." It refers to a condition whereby there is very significant wear of the rod bushing. The problem was observed in various heavy-duty engines, whereby wear exceeded 30 μm with noticeable play between the rod bushing and pin. With previous attempts to solve the problem—like implementing roundness specifications for the pin bore—the problem still prevails. Testing procedures for noise, vibration, and hardness were carried out to understand the challenge completely and to arrive at a solution. All these tests pointed to a lubrication-related root cause of the problem. Our research in this field has been largely focused on evaluating the performance of a new chevron-grooved bushing design. The validation program included a full-scale CAE simulation, proof-of-concept tests, and other design and process validation tests. This paper discusses in detail the methodology and findings from this investigation in finding a sustainable solution to arrest rod bushing wear in heavy-duty engines.

Word count: 3,497

Keywords: Pin tick, Heavy-duty engines, Rod bushing wear, Significant wear, NVH testing, Noise, Vibration, and Hardness, Lubrication, Chevron-grooved bushing, CAE simulation, Proof of Concept (POC), Design validation, Process validation, Sustainable solution, Roundness specifications, Pin bore

1. Introduction

Most of the engines are prone to inherent noise to a certain extent. Though the noise isolation systems may aid in curtailing the overall levels of noise, pockets of certain systems may remain very noisy due to design or quality or manufacture-related problems. Once, we came across this problem with a 6.4L heavy duty engine. Customers reported a 'pin tick' type noise during cold starts that typically reduced/disappeared once warm. Further investigation of this was done through subjective and objective evaluations, including instrumentation of the engine/vehicle for noise signal recording.

The first thing that came to our minds as to why the noise was happening was poor lubrication between the piston-connecting rod and the pin joint. This had been the hypothesis, based on how the engine and vehicle acted during cold starts; as the engine warms up, oil pressure increases provide enough lubrication to the joint to mitigate noise. We then ran a quality-returned engine, adding lubrication joints to the rod bushing to test this hypothesis.

It was necessary to ensure that the solution was feasible and robust by taking a detailed design-optimization approach. We compared the rod with the current plain bushing and the rod with the grooved bushing by CAE analysis. The results of simulation showed that, compared with previous concepts, the rod with the grooved bushing provided better asperity contact and film thickness to lubricate the joint; hence, it is an optimal solution.

2. Literature Review

Han et al. [1] conducted an experimental study on the tribological behavior of a variety of materials used for water-lubricated journal bearings. Their results underline that there were very clear differences in friction and wear depending on the materials, thus showing how to achieve suitable bearing performance by optimum material choices. Komori and Umehara [2] investigated the effects of diamond-like carbon coatings on friction-wear working under lubrication by engine oil. The results showed that critical surface morphology has a significant influence on tribo-chemical reactions, thus expanding the knowledge of DLC coatings within the area of reducing wear of motor components. Liang et al. [3] give a discourse on the development process of emission regulations and internal combustion engine control technologies. Their work underlined that, with enhanced stringency, the emission standards drive technological innovation toward lower environmental impacts; this underscores the critical point for transportation sustainability. Liu et al. [4] presented a comprehensive review on lubrication's effects with regards to gear performance. Among the numerous lubrication strategies making a difference in gears, such as efficiency, durability, and noise reduction, are some that give valuable insight into how to achieve improvements in mechanical system reliability. Tang et al. [5] examined the effect of surface texturing on friction and wear in lubricated steel. Their findings revealed that some types of texturing patterns could reduce friction and wear dramatically for developing more durable mechanical parts. Wong and Tung [6] presented a review on the trends in reducing friction in automotive engines from the viewpoints of surface, material, and lubricant-additive technologies. Their paper enables an understanding of the roles played by these three factors in their synergistic effects to realize large friction reduction, which provides improvements in engine efficiency.

Garcia Tobar et al. [7] did a systematic review of the application of nanoparticles in lubricants and presented evidence regarding their efficiency in reducing friction coefficients. Their results showed nanotechnology offers gigantic possibilities to improve lubricants, which could include its use for improving engine performance and life. Dmochowski and Webster [8] consider the effect of lubricant viscosity-temperature characteristics on a plain journal bearing. The results from their study indicate that optimum viscosity characteristics are necessary to ensure bearing performance, particularly when bearing operate under various thermal conditions essential for reliable mechanical systems. Vardhaman et al. [9] studied the tribological behavior of zinc oxide/MWCNTs hybrid nanomaterials as additives to lubricants. They found that there were very large reductions in friction and wear, which suggests possible improvements in the efficiency of engine oils for heavy-duty applications. Sun et al. [10] employed orthogonal experiments while carrying out the lubrication analysis for a small end bearing normally featuring in reciprocating engines. Their study gave insights on how to optimize lubrication strategies for reduced wear, thus improving performance under the different operating conditions for a reciprocating engine. Grützmacher et al. [11] presented a review of multi-scale surface texturing in the field of tribology, mainly focusing on friction and wear characteristics with improved potential. The review gives direction for further research and applications in various mechanical systems, particularly in enhancing durability to engine components. Naveed et al. [12] review the tribological performance of ionic liquids as an additive in bio lubricants. Results of studies on ionic liquids underline enhancement in lubricity, reduction of friction, and wear, making them an environmentally friendly lubricant solution for both automotive and industrial applications. Rayate [13] investigated pin-tick noise and bushing wear in heavy-duty machinery, focusing on piston pin surface finish and lubrication practices. Experimental analysis reveals that improper lubrication and surface finish contribute significantly to wear, suggesting engineering improvements for enhanced performance and durability.

3. Approach

3.1 Root cause analysis with RCA Tree

A holistic methodology of root cause analysis was followed to find out what exactly was causing the pin-tick noise and bushing wear. That approach consisted of checking in all possible failure categories: machine, measurement, man, method, mother nature, and material [14]. For each of these areas, we analyzed data and information, turning the parameter to green status if the

information was considered correct. Unfortunately, the area of incorrect lubrication remains unknown, and research has been focused on resolving this aspect and optimizing the design to rectify this area of concern.

Figure 1: Root Cause Analysis Tree

3.2 Repeat failure and confirm root cause with test

3.2.1 Subjective Test

NVH measurements gave an objective assessment of the noise levels from a warranty engine. It showed that an engine had, in relation to other cylinders, larger amplitude signals at cylinders #2 and #8, while reduced amplitude signals appeared at cylinders #1, #3, and #4. Besides this fact, all cylindrical rods exhibited more significant wear and clearance compared to other rods.

Subjectively, the noise intensity and interval decrease a lot after running three times within three days. Also, with warranty engine 5W20 oil and added lube slots for rod #8, it dropped the noise level and time interval. It was determined that using lower-viscosity oil would quicken the lubrication at the rod-pin joint, thereby reducing noise.

3.2.2 Objective NVH test

Many clients have reported knocking or ticking noise during engine startups and under loads. Part analysis showed that there was excessive clearance between the piston and rod; the highest was found to be in the piston-rod #8 assembly. The clearances for piston rods #2 and #6 were also excessive. Customer complaints were instrumented using eight accelerometers mounted on the outside cylinder bank left- and right-hand walls, along with a vehicle exterior microphone, left and right engine bay microphones, and interior vehicle microphones. The operating points tested were ambient soak cold start, cranking, high idle, warm idle with no load, and warm idle with loaded conditions. They were compared under high idle, warm idle no load, and warm idle loaded conditions between the complaint engine and a non-compliant engine.

This ticking noise was characterized as uninterruptedly clear at the vehicle interior microphone from the complaint engine during the initial high idle period and was correlated to cylinder #8 [15]. The noise faded once warm up was achieved by the engine, as shown in corresponding slides. Like part analysis, cylinder #8 showed the strongest tick noise content.

Figure2: Non-Complaint Vs. Complaint Engine Noise Signal (Odd Cylinders)

Figure3: Non-Complaint Vs. Complaint Engine Noise Signal (Even Cylinders)

3.3 Design and optimization

3.3.1 Benchmarking

We studied various engines and competitors to get an idea of the design configuration used for the rod bushing and piston pins. Further studies are required to be carried out on lubrication channels in the form of grooves. These combinations, as seen in this benchmarking, were utilized by all the engines which did not report pin ticks: solid bronze with a non-DLC pin and groove, no

bushing with DLC pin and groove, and steel-bronze with nitride pin and groove [16]. This further goes to prove that our baseline design does not give any steel-bronze bushing or any lubricating groove. This study also aided us in design selection, optimization with several alternatives available.

Parameter	6.4L Baseline	6.4L A	6.2L H	3.6L P	2.4L T	6.2L F	7.3L F	6.3L G	6.2L G	6.6L G
Peak Cylinder Pressure (Bar)	86	93.9	123	84	84	105.9	85	102.7	97.6	84.3
Bushing Contact Pressure (Mpa)	121.9	152.63	211.85	126	116	135.1	123.5	132.6	130.3	143
Rod Material	HS150	HS150	HS170M	46MnVS6	HS150	HS150	HS170M	HS150	HS150	HS170M
Bushing Type	Solid cast	Steel bronze	Solid cast	No Bush	No Bush	Steel bronze	Steel bronze	Steel bronze	Steel bronze	Steel bronze
Piston Pin Surface	DLC	Nitrided	DLC	DLC	DLC	None	None	None	None	None
Lubrication	None	Groove	None	Groove	Groove	Groove	Groove	Groove	Groove	Groove
Min/Max Clearance (um)	5.5 / 21.5	7/20	8/24	11/26	10/25	9/21	9/21	9/21	9/21	9/21

Figure 4: Competitor Benchmarking

3.3.2 CAE Analysis

The minimum friction loss can be attained by a bronze bush in hydrodynamic conditions. Even though a bronze bush proved to have caused a slightly lower friction loss as compared to the steel-bronze bush, the average difference of 0.6 W was still accounted for on the firing cylinder. However, this relatively comparable friction power loss was reflected on the non-firing cylinders. The clearances demonstrate increased friction power loss with an escalation of this clearance.

Figure 5: Film Thickness Simulation Prediction Firing Cylinders

Non-Firing Cylinders

Figure 6: Film Thickness Simulation Prediction Non-Firing Cylinders

The bushing should ideally be operated under hydrodynamic conditions, as indicated by the MOFT. The solid bronze bushing displayed a slightly lower friction loss than the steel-bronze bushing. At 4000 rpm, the average difference in friction power loss between the two bushings was 0.9 W, and at 5600 rpm, the difference was approximately 1.6 W. It is noteworthy that the friction loss decreased as the clearance increased.

Figure 7: Friction Power Loss Simulation Prediction

Figure 8: Friction Power Loss & Contact Area Simulation Prediction

3.3.3 Design Selection

The design combinations for the rod-piston assembly were assessed based on the benchmarking and simulation results. The combinations included rods with steel-bronze bushing, powder metal bushing, baseline solid bronze bushing, and piston pins with DLC and non-DLC coatings.

Design Combination	Rod	Piston Pin
Tapered rod with Steel-bronze Bushing & Non DLC Pin		
Tapered rod with solid bronze bushing & Non DLC pin		
Tapered rod with powder metal bushing & Non DLC pin		
Tapered rod with cast solid bronze bushing & DLC pin		

Table 1: Proof of Concept Test Design Combinations

3.3.4 POC Test

Undertaking a proof-of-concept (POC) test following the conclusions of the component acceptance evaluation (CAE) was deemed the most prudent course of action, rather than conducting a comprehensive engine test. The POC test lasted for a duration

of 20 hours and comprised combinations of the least favorable dyno test cycle. During the POC test, we assessed the performance of four distinct rod bushing and piston pin configurations, including the base model, to identify the most effective combination.

Figure 9: Brushing Wear Comparison for POC Test

Figure 10: Pin Bore Wear Comparison for POC Test

Following the proof-of-concept (POC) testing, the steel-bronze rod bushing in combination with the non-DLC piston pin was determined to be the optimal solution. This combination resulted in the lowest levels of bushing and pin wear, making it the most suitable option.

Following the POC, only two design combinations were selected for further evaluation. One of these options was a baseline, designed to confirm the repeatability and validity of the steel-bronze bushing and non-DLC pin combination.

Design Combination	Rod	Piston Pin
Tapered rod with Steel-bronze Bushing & Non DLC Pin		
Tapered rod with cast solid bronze bushing & DLC pin		

Table 2: Design combinations selected after Proof-Of-Concept Test

3.3.5 Design Validation Test

After the completion of the proof of concept, this design had undergone an extended validation phase with tests such as MDS, Peak Power, and General Durability. The MDS test was a split test where parts were made in both the new and baseline designs. Results from the MDS test showed that rod- and pin-bore wear were better on the new design combination compared to the baseline combination. The eclectically tuned peak power engine run that followed showed very close results to the new design, indicating extremely low wear on parts.

MDS (400hr) # ESB810A

Figure11: Bushing & Pin Bore Wear for MDS Test

Peak Power (200 hr) #ESB808A

Figure 12: Bushing & Pin Bore Wear for Peak Power Test

The hot scuff was on another critical schedule, and the parts were made at minimum dimensions and clearance, which proved to be successful. The longer general durability test proved successful, with favorable results.

Hot Scuff (6 hr) #ESB809A

Figure 13: Bushing & Pin Bore Wear for Hot Scuff Test

GED (511 hr) # ESB817A

Figure 14: Bushing & Pin Bore Wear for GED Test

3.3.6 Design Validation: Friction Transparency Test

This study was aimed at benchmarking the frictional performance of a newly designed engine component against a baseline design. Since this new design showed very high performance in reducing wear, it is pertinent to establish whether this comes with the penalty of higher friction to the engine.

The engine was run at various important speed points in the drive cycle: 1000, 2500, and 4000 rpm. Moreover, the motoring friction was measured by utilizing an operating engine with the wide-open throttle test. To ensure the preciseness of the data and reliability, the experiment ran on the same engine with both new designs and baseline design.

Figure 15: Dynamic torque/friction comparison between new and current bushing-pin combination at 1000 rpm

Figure 16: Dynamic torque/friction comparison between new and current bushing-pin combination at 2500 rpm

Figure 17: Dynamic torque/friction comparison between new and current bushing-pin combination at 4000 rpm

Figure 18: Dynamic torque/friction comparison between new and current bushing-pin combination under WOT run

3.3.7 Process Validation Test

Where after the design validation had been completed, there was actual initiation for production validation. This employed special tooling for rod parent bores and that for bushing bores. Once the production line had formally been changed and the process updated for the new design, another test was done as a process validation. It involved running the same dyno test with an identical dynamometer used in the design validation test and observing any consistency in wear performance.

Results from this MDS and peak power testing displayed improved rod- and pin-bore wear over the previous design combination. Implementation of the new design combination to production required unique tooling for both rod parent bores and bushing bores. Of course, a new round of testing had to be done in process validation once the production line had been changed officially and the process updated. This included repeating the dyno test that was conducted during the design validation phase and confirming the wear performance remained within expectation.

Figure 19: Bushing & Pin Bore Wear for MDS Test

Figure 20: Figure 14: Bushing & Pin Bore Wear for Peak Power Test

The outcomes of both the Hot scuff and general durability cycles were favorable, demonstrating that the rod bushing-pin bore wear was below the prescribed limit.

Figure 21: Figure 14: Bushing & Pin Bore Wear for Hot Scuff Test

Figure 22: Figure 14: Bushing & Pin Bore Wear for GED Test

4. Conclusion

In summary, proper research and optimization processes have been followed and documented in this paper with respect to the wear of the rod bushing and related "pin tick" noise concerns with the 6.4 L heavy-duty engine. A new solution has been rightly identified and validated through a disciplined process that included root cause analysis, subjective and objective testing, and rigorous design and process validation of that solution. Among them, it is seen that a chevron-grooved bushing design, in combination with the steel-bronze material and a non-DLC piston pin, shows the best performance with respect to bushing wear and noise reduction. Clearly, this showcases better performance not only due to wear reduction but also through engine efficiency without giving way on friction levels. That this solution has been successfully implemented is a guarantee not only of the reliability and customer satisfaction with the 6.4L Heavy-Duty engine but also sets a benchmark on how to fix prevalent challenges in many other applications within the automotive industry. These findings bring out the importance of adopting a

holistic, integrated approach to solving engineering challenges by coupling advanced simulation techniques with empirical testing to ensure durable and effective solutions.

5. Future Work

This solution will be integrated into the production processes of each supplier in the future by upgrading the production line with the required dies, gauges, and tools. Once this has been done, a production engineering assessment will then be made at the engine plant to ensure changes do not affect the process of assembling engines in any manner. The output of this project would be used in revising the part design book guidelines by adding the lubrication grooves on the rod bushing joint. Moreover, DLC coatings, proven otherwise should not be preferred for piston coatings. Similar solutions would also be explored for other programs and new ones.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

Pin tick: A noise characterized by significant wear in the rod bushing.

Rod bushing: A component in the engine subject to wear and play between it and the pin.

NVH: Noise, Vibration, and Harshness.

CAE: Computer-Aided Engineering.

POC: Proof of Concept.

Lubrication: The application of a substance (such as oil) to minimize friction and wear between surfaces in contact.

Chevron-grooved bushing: A type of bushing design evaluated for its effectiveness in reducing wear.

RCA: Root Cause Analysis.

MDS: Mechanical Durability Specification.

WOT: Wide Open Throttle.

CQI: Customer Quality Index.

DLC: Diamond-Like Carbon (referring to a type of coating).

MOFT: Minimum Oil Film Thickness.

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